

Using LLMs to Apply a Cultural Event Taxonomy for Spatial Inference from Unstructured Platform Data

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Abstract

Ticketing platforms record large volumes of geographically referenced cultural events, yet weakly structured descriptions and limited alignment with official socio-economic datasets constrain their use in spatial analysis. This study proposes an LLM-assisted workflow for classifying approximately 87,000 Eventbrite listings in Greater London into a cultural event taxonomy aligned with the DCMS SIC-based framework of the cultural sector. We evaluate classification reliability and aggregate the results at the MSOA level, enabling thematic clustering and geographically weighted regression with local social and economic indicators. Our analysis reveals that different categories of cultural events exhibit distinct spatial distributions and neighbourhood associations, including varying relationships with centrality, demographic composition, and local commercial environments. PCA and clustering identify three specialised cultural types, Sport, Spirituality & Religion, and Craft, whose spatial patterns diverge from the main group and respond differently to neighbourhood characteristics. Methodologically, the study contributes a reproducible GeoAI approach for constructing spatially analysable datasets from unstructured event data.

Keywords: Large Language Models (LLMs), GeoAI, Urban analytics, Cultural events, Ticketing platforms

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) offer new opportunities to exploit unstructured urban data generated by digital platforms (De Sabbata et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2024). However, textual data often lack a consistent and comparable structure, limiting their aggregation across space, linkage to neighbourhood-level indicators, and use in quantitative geographic analysis (Janowicz et al., 2020). Cultural events provide a cogent example: they are inherently place-based phenomena and increasingly mediated through ticketing platforms that combine rich textual descriptions with precise locations (Black et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025). Event-type information on these platforms is frequently incomplete, organiser-defined, inconsistent, and multilingual, which prevents reliable categorisation and limits category-specific spatial analysis and neighbourhood-level inference.

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Cultural events generate a measurable footprint of cultural life in cities (Benzecry & Collins, 2014; Feder et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025) and can complement traditional measures of cultural infrastructure and participation (GLA, 2023; DCMS, 2024). However, definitions of cultural events vary widely across policy frameworks, academic traditions, and commercial platform taxonomies (DCMS, 2022; SOLT, 2022; Williams, 1977), complicating comparison and evaluation. A coherent, domain-specific taxonomy would be instrumental to support analysis and aggregation of platform-based cultural events compatible with UK data on cultural participation (AHRC, 2023).

Choosing Greater London as an analytically rich case of a vibrant cultural event system, we aim to demonstrate how LLM-assisted classification can translate unstructured event descriptions into an analytically coherent dataset suitable for large-scale spatial analysis (*Figure 1*). Three research questions guide this study:

RQ1. How can a cultural event taxonomy be designed and applied using LLMs to translate unstructured ticketing-platform text into categories for integration with ancillary socio-economic datasets?

RQ2. To what extent can LLMs apply such a taxonomy to weakly structured event descriptions with reliability and scalability?

RQ3. Using structured cultural event data labelled by this taxonomy, what spatial associational patterns and MSOA-level relationships of cultural events become analysable?

2. Methods

The workflow in *Figure 1* proceeds in three stages: taxonomy design, LLM-assisted classification, and spatial analysis, each addressing one research question. We collected a dataset of over 87,000 events from Eventbrite, a high-volume, weakly structured source in which event-type information is incomplete, inconsistent, or organiser-specific. To answer RQ1, we developed a 20-category event taxonomy (*Table 1*) through an iterative reconciliation of platform-native categories with official industrial and survey-based classifications. Eventbrite's own category labels served as the initial vocabulary, cross-referenced with Ticketmaster's genre structure to identify gaps and inconsistencies across platforms. The resulting set was expanded and realigned to the cultural, creative, and tourism sub-sectors defined by the DCMS Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) framework (2022), ensuring coverage of activities recognised as culturally significant in UK policy contexts. The proposed categories are compared with national cultural consumption categories in the DCMS Taking Part (2021) and Participation surveys (2024) to ensure alignment with national audience data. Finally, each category was matched to a specific SIC code (DCMS, 2022) to enable linkage with official economic datasets in future research.

Figure 1. Research design

To answer RQ2, we designed a few-shot prompting strategy to classify event descriptions into predefined event categories. GPT-4.1-mini and GPT-5-mini were used for different tasks, selected based on model availability over the project timeline and cost considerations, while maintaining consistent prompt design and evaluation procedures. The two-stage evaluation (tag quality and category classification) together form a robust approach (*Tables 2 and 3*). First, each event was assigned a set of cultural tags generated by GPT-4.1-mini (*Table 2*) from the combined textual tuple (event name, description). We drew a random sample of 400 events from the full Eventbrite dataset (approximately 87,000 records) for evaluation. The sample size was determined using Cochran’s formula for estimating a proportion with a 5% margin of error at the 95% confidence level, assuming a conservative proportion of $p = 0.5$. This yields a required sample of around 384 observations for a population of this size, which we rounded up to 400. The sampled events’ cultural tags were manually assessed by three authors, resulting in an estimated tagging accuracy of approximately 95%.

Table 1. Cultural event taxonomy aligned with Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) sectors

<i>DCMS SIC sector</i>	<i>Event category</i>
<i>Music, performing and visual arts</i>	Theatre & drama
	Dance
	Opera
	Music
<i>Film, TV, video, radio and photography</i>	Film
<i>Music, performing and visual arts</i>	Visual arts
<i>Crafts</i>	Craft
<i>Design and designer fashion</i>	Fashion
<i>Museums and galleries</i>	Museum & Gallery
<i>Publishing</i>	Literature
<i>Library and archives</i>	Library
	Archive
<i>Education / Commercial activities</i>	Science
	Technology
<i>Amusement and recreation activities</i>	Lifestyle
<i>Tour operator activities</i>	Tourism
<i>Social work / Other service activities</i>	Community
	Charity
<i>Activities of religious organisations</i>	Spirituality & religion
<i>Sport Activities</i>	Sport

Second, using the tuple (event name, cultural tags) as input, a GPT-5-mini classifier with a few-shot prompt assigned each event a ranked sequence of category predictions. As shown in *Table 3*, each event was ultimately assigned to a single category, forming the basis for subsequent spatial and cluster analyses. Using manually annotated top-level event categories as ground truth, we evaluated GPT-5-mini and a BART-MNLI baseline using precision, recall, and F1 under a single-label multiclass setting, reporting macro-averaged scores to account for category imbalance. GPT-5-mini substantially outperforms the BART-large-mnli baseline, achieving a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.91 compared to 0.50, indicating more reliable performance across both common and infrequent cultural event categories.

To address RQ3, the validated LLM-based classifier is applied to the full dataset to generate a large-scale labelled event corpus for spatial analysis. MSOA-level event counts are first modelled using spatial negative binomial mixed models incorporating a Matérn spatial random field over MSOA centroids via an SPDE mesh to account for overdispersion, followed by Multiscale Geographically Weighted Regression (MGWR) to assess scale-dependent effects. Initial diagnostics reveal significant spatial autocorrelation in model residuals, indicating unaccounted spatial structure. Across specifications, accessibility, centrality, ethnic composition, population density, workplace activity, and commercial amenities show robust associations with event intensity.

Table 2. LLM-assisted cultural tag extraction pipeline and performance

Component	Details
<i>Data</i>	400 event descriptions (random sampled)
<i>Model</i>	GPT-4.1-mini
<i>API</i>	OpenAI Batch API
<i>Role</i>	Expert in Natural Language Processing
<i>Inputs</i>	event_name (string), event_description (string)
<i>Goal</i>	Extract cultural tags from event descriptions
<i>Rules</i>	Use only the provided event descriptions to extract cultural tags
<i>Output format</i>	Valid JSON with a list of cultural tags
<i>API Messages</i>	Few-shot User & Assistant messages
<i>Performance</i>	Precision = 0.951 Recall = 0.943 F1score = 0.947

Table 3. LLM-assisted event classification pipeline and performance

Component	Experiment Details	Baseline Details
<i>Data</i>	400 event descriptions (random sampled)	Same as experiment group
<i>Model</i>	GPT-5-mini	Bart-large-mnli
<i>API</i>	OpenAI Batch API	Hugging Face
<i>Role</i>	Expert in cultural event classification	Zero-shot text classifier
<i>Inputs</i>	event_name (string), event_tags (list of strings)	Same as experiment group
<i>Category set</i>	20 predefined cultural categories with textual definitions	Same as experiment group
<i>Goal</i>	Rank all categories by relevance to the event	Same as experiment group
<i>Confidence labels</i>	High / Middle / Low	Confidence score
<i>Rules</i>	Use only provided inputs and predefined categories	N/A
<i>Output format</i>	Valid JSON with ordered category–confidence pairs	Same as experiment group
<i>API Messages</i>	Few-shot User & Assistant messages	N/A
<i>Performance</i>	Precision = 0.899 Recall = 0.943 F1score = 0.911	Precision = 0.607 Recall = 0.492 F1score = 0.501

3. Results and Discussions

Table 4 shows the relationship between cultural events and socio-economic variables at the local level by estimating a spatial Negative Binomial Generalised Linear Mixed Model. While retaining the same census-derived covariates as the non-spatial Negative Binomial Generalised Linear Model, our model adds a continuous spatial effect to capture local dependence. This

substantially improved spatial diagnostics: Moran's I of the randomised quantile residuals dropped from significant positive autocorrelation to near zero and non-significant ($I = 0.0065$, $p = 0.35$), indicating that residual spatial structure was effectively absorbed.

Table 4. Spatial negative binomial generalised linear mixed model (NB GLMM) results. All covariates are z-standardised. Estimates are on the log scale. Approx_Effect reports the approximate change in event count per MSOA associated with a one standard-deviation increase in each covariate, evaluated at the sample mean event count per MSOA (≈ 88), calculated as $88 \times (\exp(\hat{\beta}_j) - 1)$.

Variable	Estimate	Std_Error	Std_Dev	Approx_Effect
(Intercept)	3.58	0.075		
Accessibility Index (PTAL)	0.301	0.062	10.662	$\approx +30$ events
Distance to central London	-0.515	0.070	5.766	≈ -35 events
Workday population	-0.394	0.053	5674.635	≈ -28 events
Workplace population	0.368	0.057	4274.832	$\approx +40$ events
Outside-UK migrants (%)	-0.028	0.058	1.608	≈ -3 events
Within-UK migrants (%)	0.349	0.066	5.835	$\approx +36$ events
Economically active population (%)	-0.067	0.046	5.404	≈ -6 events
Pubs/Bars count	0.148	0.062	8.73	$\approx +14$ events
Supermarkets count	0.246	0.038	2.07	$\approx +24$ events
Dispersion_parameter	1.680			
Matern_range	3.460			
Spatial_SD	0.588			
ML_criterion	4618.457			

To examine whether these associations are spatially uniform or vary across London, a multiscale geographically weighted regression (MGWR) was subsequently fitted, allowing each covariate's effect to operate at its own spatial scale. MGWR results further indicate that cultural event distribution is driven by a small set of spatially varying mechanisms, which are layered on broadly stable structural factors. Accessibility and workplace population act as broadly positive structural drivers of event intensity, while workday population shows a consistent negative association, reflecting residential-dominated areas with fewer event venues. In contrast, the workplace population exhibits clear spatial heterogeneity, with a strong positive association in northern and southeastern areas, but weak or negative effects in central London, likely reflecting space constraints and competition with large, venue-based cultural clusters.

While the preceding models treat all cultural events as a single outcome, different cultural forms may cluster in distinct ways across the city. To investigate this, PCA and k-means clustering were applied to MSOA-level category counts. PCA reveals that most cultural forms cluster near the centre of component space, reflecting broadly mainstream activities distributed widely across London, while Sport, Spirituality & Religion, and Craft occupy extreme positions along the first three principal components, indicating distinctive spatial signatures as in *Figure 3*. A four-cluster solution in *Figure 4*, supported by the highest silhouette score ($k = 4: 0.62$; $k = 3: 0.53$; $k = 5: 0.51$), identifies one dominant mainstream cluster alongside three specialised clusters characterised by high-engagement sport, demographically concentrated spirituality, and hyper-local craft production. Cluster-level negative binomial models and Moran's I further indicate that these cultural types respond differently to neighbourhood characteristics and exhibit spatial coherence not fully explained by MSOA-level covariates.

Events per Hex (1 km²) by Category

Data source: Eventbrite (2024.03 - 2025.02)

Figure 3. Distribution of cultural events by category in Greater London

Figure 4. K-means clustering analysis of event categories' distribution on MSOA levels

4. Conclusion

This study develops and validates an LLM-assisted workflow that classifies large volumes of unstructured event descriptions using a domain- and policy-aligned cultural taxonomy. The workflow is designed to produce consistent, model-ready data through explicit prompt design, rule-based post-processing, and evaluation against a manually labelled sample. This setup improves reproducibility and allows classification uncertainty and potential model biases to be explicitly assessed rather than treated as noise. By structuring event data at the MSOA level, the pipeline makes platform-derived data compatible with census and policy datasets, enabling their use in spatial modelling (Batty, 2025).

Substantively, the resulting dataset supports analysis of how different types of cultural events are distributed across Greater London and how they relate to local characteristics. Linking classified event counts to local covariates reveals that the drivers of event intensity vary across categories, rather than following a single uniform pattern. Spatial modelling shows that accessibility, proximity to central London, and local commercial amenities are broadly associated with higher event intensity, while clustering reveals that specialised cultural types such as Sport, Spirituality & Religion, and Craft diverge from this mainstream pattern. This provides a more differentiated view of urban cultural activity than analyses based on raw platform categories. While both platform data and LLM classification introduce biases (Wright et al., 2026), the framework makes these sources of bias explicit and can be extended to multi-platform and longitudinal settings for comparative analysis.

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